

Technical Efficiency of Rabbit Production among Small Holder Farmers in Ivo Local Government Area of Ebonyi State, Nigeria

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Abstract

The study measured the level of technical efficiency and its determinants among rabbit farmers in Ivo Local Government Area of Ebonyi State, Nigeria using stochastic frontier production function. Multi-stage sampling technique was used to select 60 rabbit farmers from which data were collected using well-structured questionnaire and oral interview. The estimated technical efficiency of rabbit farmers ranged from 56% to 95.0% with a mean of 23.0%. The educational level, rearing experience and access to credit were the determinants of technical efficiency of the rabbit farmers. There is a need in Improving farmers' access to education, credits and drugs and vaccines at lower costs in order to enhance farmers' technical efficiency for the sustainability of rabbit production especially now the conventional livestock is becoming costly.

Keywords; Technical efficiency, Rabbit Production, Small Holder Farmers

Introduction

Livestock production is an important sector in the Nigeria national development in producing food, increasing external trade, ensuring a balanced development between areas and sectors, and reducing unemployment in rural areas, in addition to creating new employment opportunities in the industrial and service sectors (Anochili and Onuoha, 2007). In a recent time in Nigeria, the animal protein supply in the Nigerian diet especially in the rural areas remain inadequate. In an attempt to balance the deficit from the domestic supply, successive government of Nigeria has engaged on meat imports to the neglect of the development and sustenance of the local livestock industry to the detriment of the nation's meagre resources (Moreki et al. 2011). Rabbit ,a moogastic animal of the family *Leopondge* and of the order *Lagomorpha* has been identified as an economy livestock that could bridge the wide gap in dietary protein intake in most developing countries (Nworgu and Hammend, 2009). This could be associated to its intrinsic features including high rate of reproduction; early maturity; small body sized; rapid growth rate comparable to that of broiler chicken (Hassan and Owolabi, 2009) high genetic selection potential; efficient feed and land space utilization, limited competition with humans for similar food and high quality nutritious meat (high protein content, low fat content, low cholesterol content, low sodium (Na) content, low amount of saturated fatty acid, fine texture, Low bone to meat ratio and high digestibility) (Ozor and Madukwe, 2005). Rabbit has the ability to turn forage into high protein and yet remains within the investment ranges of the poorest families and producing about 47 kg of meat per doe per year (Moreki et al. 2011)

Despite the importance of the animal, rabbit production in most developing countries are beset with problems of high cost of concentrates, relatively smaller weight gain during the dry season pests and disease (komolafe et al 2009), non availability of market when the farmers are ready to sell their stock and inadequate knowledge and information about the advantages of eating rabbit meat (Nworgu and Hammed, 2009, Okorie, 2011). Also forage availability sometimes is the limiting factor in rabbit production especially conventional forage such as groundnut hay in which there is competition between the rabbit and ruminant animals (Jithendran, 2007)). These result in low production and productivity of rabbit production and in effect unable to meet up its role in economic development.

Nevertheless, to improve the farmers' productivity requires that their resources must be used more efficiently with attention paid to the ability to produce a given level of output with a minimum quantity of

inputs(technical efficiency). This efficiency type can be measured either as input conserving oriented technical efficiency or output-expanding oriented technical efficiency (Jondrow *et al.*, 1982; Ali, 1996). Estimation of the level of technical efficiency helps to determine if the deviation in technical efficiency from the frontier output is due to specific factor or external random factor (Kolawole, 2009). Specifically, the objectives were to describe the socio economic characteristics of the farmers, estimate the rabbit farmers' technical efficiency and the determinant factors, estimate the profitability of rabbit production and identify the production constraint to rabbit production in the study area.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Ivo Local Government Area of Ebonyi State, Nigeria was studied. It is located at latitude $5^{\circ}56''$ and $6^{\circ}59'N$ and longitude $7^{\circ}35'$ and $7^{\circ}4E$. Its rainfall ranges from 1500-2500mm, temperature of $28-45^{\circ}C$ and moderate relative humidity of 75%. Ivo L.G.A comprises of seven (7) autonomous communities and many villages. It covers an area of 350 km^2 with a population of 220, 919 people (NPC 2006). The Ivo Local Government Area people are mainly farmers and engage in other economic activities. Data utilized for this study were primarily sourced and were obtained from farmers using questionnaire. A total of 60 rabbit farmers were randomly sampled from six communities where the rabbit is reared. Baseline information on socio-economic characteristics input use and output levels were collected and analysed. The objectives I, and ii were addressed with percentage response and Cobb Douglas stochastic production function The Cobb Douglas frontier production function is specified by (Onyenweaku *et al.*, 2010) as follows:

$$\ln Q = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \ln x_1 + \beta_2 \ln x_2 + \beta_3 \ln x_3 + \beta_4 \ln x_4 + \beta_5 \ln x_5 + V_1 + U_1 \dots \dots (1)$$

Where Q = value of output of farmers (N), X_1 = doe and bulk (No); X_2 = feed use (kg); X_3 = labour Input (man days); X_4 = x_4 = drug and medication (litres); X_5 = water required (liters), x_6 = capital depreciation (N), V_i = Error term not under the control of the farmer, U_i = error term under the control of farmer, β_0 = intercept, $\beta_1 - \beta_2$ = parameters to be estimated. In order to determine factors contributing to the observed technical efficiency, the following model was formulated and estimated jointly with a stochastic frontier model in maximum likelihood estimation procedure using the computer software frontier version 4.1 (5).

$$TE = a + d_1 m_1 + a_2 m_2 + a_3 m_3 + a_4 m_4 + a_5 m_5 + a_6 m_6 + a_n m_n.$$

Where TE = Technical efficiency, X_1 = planting material (cassava cuttings) (bundles), X_2 = fertilizer (kg), M_1 = age of the farmers (years), M_2 = educational level (years), M_3 = farming experience (years), M_4 = household size (Number), M_5 = extension visit (Number), M_6 = membership of cooperative (1 = members, 0 = non member), $a_0 - a_6$ are parameters to be estimated.

Results and Discussion

The mean statistics of rabbit farmers are shown in table I. On the average, a typical rabbit farmer is 24.2 years old with 12 years of education, 16 years of rabbit production experience with the average stock size of 14.6 animals. The mean household size was 7 persons with average annual income of ₦48, 620 and mean output of 320 rabbits for eight months. The maximum livelihood estimates (M/E) of the stochastic frontier production parameters for urban broiler farmers is presented in table 2. The total variance (σ) was 0.8701 which is significantly different from zero at 1% level. This implies goodness of fit of the model and the correctness of the specified distribution assumption of the composite error term. The variance ratio parameter is estimated at 0.6027 which is also statistically significant at 1% probability level, indicating that 60.2% of the total variation in rabbit output is due to technical inefficiency.

As expected the coefficients of the rabbit feed, labour inputs, water use and drug and medication as contained in Table 2 had the desired positive signs and were statistically significant at 1.0% probability level. The implication is that the more of these inputs used, the more the matured rabbit accruing to the farmers, *ceteris paribus*. The maximum likelihood estimate of the determinants of the technical inefficiency of rabbit farmers is presented in Table 2 and revealed that the coefficient of educational level showed a positive relationship with technical efficiency and statistically significant at 1% risk level. The positive relationship

between the coefficient of the level of schooling and technical efficiency according to Onyenweaku, (2010) was borne out of the notion that education tends to make people more receptive to innovations, risk averse and prudent in resources management. Ume *et al.* 2010, Eze and Akpa 2010), made similar finding, Therefore, policies for ensuring education attainment amongst farm households through enhanced formal and informal educational programmes would impact positively on farmers' efficiency and therefore should be encouraged. In addition, farming experience coefficient was positive in line with a priori expectation and concurred with Tanko, (2004), who opined that farmer with long years of rearing experiences tend to combine their resources better in an optimal manner and could help them to set realistic goals.

Moreover, the coefficient of credit access had a direct relationship with technical efficiency of rabbit farmers at 95% confidence interval and synonymous with the findings of **Onifade et al** (2009) on rabbit production status and promotion strategies. They opined that Agricultural credit has the potential to enhance efficient resource allocation, permits application of technology, reduces post harvest wastes and stabilizes farm input prices, farm income and enhance efficient marketing of agricultural products. In contrary, Onyenweaku *et al.* (2010) found a negative relationship between the coefficient of credit and technical efficiency. Such sign identity could be linked to poor access to credit facilities by most farmers, especially in sub Saharan Africa.

The statistical test of the coefficient of extension contact was negative and significant at 5% risk level. The bottle neck the extension agents encountered in discharging their duties as asserted by Eze and Akpa, (2010) could be the reason for the negative sign of the variable. Extension is voluntary, informal, out-of school educational process which aims to teach rural people how to improve their level of living by their own efforts, through making wise use of the resources at their disposal and better system of farming and home making for the benefit of the individual, the family community and the nation as a whole (Ume, et al 2010). Membership of organization had a negative relationship with the farmers' technical efficiency and significant at 10% probability level. The distractions from farming activities by organizations' matters could be linked to the signing identity. However, various studies had found a positive relationship between members organisation and technical efficiency (Onyenweaku et al.; 2010; Eze and Akpa, 2010). They opined that cooperative is a source of good quality inputs, training, information and organized marketing of production, which are capable of enhancing farmers' efficiency

The distribution of the technical efficiency estimates obtained from the stochastic frontier is presented in Table 4. The Table indicated that the rabbit farmers mean efficiency was 56%, which implied that there was a large scope for increasing cocoyam production by 44%, by adopting the techniques and technology employed by the best practice cocoyam farmers. According to Onyenweaku et al. (2010) farmers who had efficiency values above the mean score were frontier farmers, while those who had values below it were non-frontier farmers. As such, the percentage of the frontier farmers was 59.76 percent, while non-frontier cocoyam producers represented 38.39 percent. The implication of the result was that the average cocoyam farmer required 41.1% $(1-0.56/0.95)^{100}$ cost saving to attain the status of the most efficient cocoyam farmer as sampled best ten categories, while the least performing farmer needed 75.8% $(1-0.23/0.95)^{100}$ cost saving to become the most efficient cocoyam producer among the worst 10 sampled farmers.

The elasticity and return to scale for rabbit production is shown in table 5. The regression coefficients in the Cobb Douglas stochastic production frontier function are the elasticity, and their sums indicate the return to scale (Eze and Akpa, 2010). The return to scales (production elasticity) has a function coefficient of 1.4782. This implies that rabbit production farmers' production plan is elastic. Hence the farmers are in stage two of production function phase. This could be as a result of high and positive coefficient of feed with a low and positive coefficient of depreciation. This implies that rabbit utilizes their scarce resource, particularly feed in their production process. Furthermore, on the individual production, input elasticity showed that change in the rabbit (doe and sow), labour, the size of farm land and capital employed by 1 unit brought about a change in

opposite direction of 0.0682, 0.0421, 0.0077 and 0.0131 in the output of broiler respectively. In the same way, a unit change in feeds intake brought about a change in opposite direction of 1.3471 in the output of rabbit

Conclusion and Recommendations

The following conclusions were deduced from the study; Most of the respondents studied were youths married and educated. Also, the factors that affect the output of rabbit were farm size, labour, feed and capital in the form of credit. The determinants of the farmers' technical efficiency were educational level, farming experience, and credit.

1. The positive influence of education on farmer's efficiency has been noted, in this direction, there is need to strengthen the current policies on education such as the universal basic education, adult education, and nomadic education
2. There is a need to increase farmers' access to credit through micro-finance and other formal sources at the reduced interest rate.
3. There is a need to encourage both experienced and new entrants in rabbit production through provision of improved inputs at subsidized prices.
4. Extension agent must be motivated to carry out their functions judiciously

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Table 1: Mean socioeconomic statistics of Enugu urban broiler farmers

Variable	Mean value
Age of urban broiler farmer (yrs)	37.2
Educational level (yrs)	12
Farming experience	16
Farm size (ha)	21.4
Household size	7
Annual income (₦)	₦48,284
Output	420

Source: Field Survey, 2016

Table 2: Estimated stochastic production function for broiler farmers in Enugu urban

Production Factor	Parameter	Coefficient	Standard error	t-ratio
Constant term	β_0	2.316	0.434	5.423***
Doe and sow	β_1	2.319	0.437	5.425***
Feed used	β_2	-2.067	0.549	-3.766***
Labour input	β_3	0.2536	0.0681	3.7243***
Drug and medicine	β_4	0.0042	0.0018	2.326**
Water requirement	β_5	0.0145	0.0075	1.9266*
Capital depreciation	β_6	0.0520	0.0227	-2.2916
Diagnostic statistics				
Total variance	q^2	0.8701		
Variance ratio	γ	0.6027		
Likelihood ratio test				
Los log likelihood				

Source: Field Survey, 2016 *** = significant at 1% , ** = significant at 5% , * = significant at 10%

Table 3: Estimated determinant of technical inefficiency in broiler farmers in Enugu urban

Determinants	Parameter	Coefficient	Standard error	t-ratio
Age of farmer	a_1	-0.0099	0.0394	-0.2512
Farm size	a_2	0.0928	0.0636	1.4148
Household size	a_3	0.0143	0.0049	2.9184
Educational level	a_4	2.9577	0.4013	7.36***
Farming experience	a_5	0.6912	0.0912	7.5759***
Access to credit	a_6	-0.1023	0.1963	0.5211
Extension contact	a_7	-0.0520	0.0227	-2.2916**
Membership of organisation	a_8	0.0145	0.0075	1.9266*

Source: Computed from Field Survey, 2016

*** = significant at 1% , ** = significant at 5% and * = significant at 10%

Table 4: Distribution of Technical Efficiency Index

Technical Efficiency Index	Frequency	Percentage
0.00 – 0.20	15	12.5
0.21 – 0.40	11	9.17
0.41 – 0.60	30	25.00
0.61 – 0.80	35	45.83
0.81 - 1.00	9	7.5
Maximum Technical Efficiency	0.95	
Minimum technical efficiency	0.23	
Mean technical efficiency	0.56	
Mean of the best 10	43.4	
Mean of the worst 10	75.8	

Source: Computed from Field Survey, 2016

Table 5: Elasticity and return to scale for Rabbit production in Ivo LGA

Production inputs	Elasticity
Feeds	1.3471
Doe and	0.0682
Labour	0.0421
Farm size	0.0077
Depreciation	0.0131
Return to scale	1.4782

Source: Field Survey data, 2016